

Comparative Analysis of Subclinical Hypothyroidism in Patients with and Without Metabolic Syndrome

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Abstract:

At Dr. S N Medical College, Jodhpur, 200 patients with and without metabolic syndrome were analysed for two years to determine the prevalence of subclinical hypothyroidism. In the metabolic syndrome group (22%), subclinical hypothyroidism was more common than in the control group (8%), with increased TSH but normal free T4 levels. These findings imply that thyroid function and metabolic abnormalities are closely related, highlighting the potential benefits of thyroid monitoring in metabolic syndrome management. The study suggests coordinated care to reduce metabolic and thyroid dysfunction health concerns.

Keywords: Subclinical Hypothyroidism, Metabolic Syndrome, Thyroid Screening, Cardiovascular Risk.

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Introduction

Subclinical hypothyroidism is a disease when thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) levels are high, but thyroid hormone levels in the blood are normal [1]. It is a subtle and frequently symptomless condition that can have important health consequences. This condition has been found to coincide with several metabolic disorders, including metabolic syndrome, which is a collection of conditions such as elevated blood pressure, high blood sugar, excessive abdominal fat, and abnormal cholesterol levels [2,3]. The correlation between subclinical hypothyroidism and metabolic syndrome is of significant interest due to the shared association with heightened cardiovascular risk and other metabolic disruptions [4].

This comparative study seeks to clarify the frequency and features of subclinical hypothyroidism in patients with metabolic syndrome in comparison to those without metabolic syndrome. This research aims to investigate the thyroid function in these two groups in order to discover potential underlying mechanisms that could explain the relationship between thyroid dysfunction and the components of metabolic syndrome [5]. Gaining a comprehensive understanding of these connections is essential for the development of precise therapies that can effectively reduce the risks associated with both illnesses and enhance patient outcomes [6].

The importance of investigating this correlation resides in the possibility of identifying and implementing intervention strategies at an earlier stage for populations at risk. This could result in improved management of both subclinical hypothyroidism and metabolic syndrome, ultimately reducing the overall impact of cardiovascular and metabolic diseases [7,8].

Methodology

Study Design: This cross-sectional study compares subclinical hypothyroidism in metabolic syndrome and non-metabolic syndrome participants.

Study Population: This study will enrol 200 outpatients from Dr. S N Medical College, Jodhpur. The study population will be split in two:

1. 100 patients diagnosed with metabolic syndrome using NCEP ATP III criteria.
2. 100 non-metabolic syndrome control patients.

Inclusion Criteria

- Adults 18-65 years old. Participants will be male and female.
- Patients with metabolic syndrome must meet three of the five NCEP ATP III criteria.

Exclusion Criteria

- Thyroid illness or medicines.

Women pregnant.

- Cancer, chronic kidney disease, and heart failure patients.

Study Duration: The study will be conducted over a period of two years, allowing for adequate time to recruit participants and conduct thorough follow-up assessments.

Data Collection: Each participant's medical history, physical exam, and lab tests will be reviewed to collect data. Every participant will be measured for these parameters: Thyroid function testing with TSH and free T4.
- Fasting glucose, HDL cholesterol, triglycerides, and blood pressure for metabolic syndrome. BMI and waist circumference.

Laboratory Tests: Blood samples will be collected after an overnight fast and analyzed for thyroid function tests and metabolic syndrome parameters using standardized laboratory techniques.

Statistical Analysis: Descriptive statistics will summarise data. Both groups' subclinical hypothyroidism prevalence will be calculated. Both groups will be compared using Chi-square tests for categorical variables and t-tests for continuous variables. Multivariate logistic regression will control for variables and examine the metabolic syndrome-subclinical hypothyroidism relationship. P-values below 0.05 indicate statistical significance

Results

The study effectively enrolled 200 volunteers, evenly divided into two cohorts: those with metabolic syndrome (n=100) and individuals without metabolic syndrome (n=100). The demographic analysis indicated that there were no notable disparities in age and gender between the two groups, thereby confirming their comparability.

Prevalence of Subclinical Hypothyroidism:

Subclinical hypothyroidism was found in 22% of the individuals diagnosed with metabolic syndrome, while only 8% of the control group without metabolic syndrome had this condition. The observed discrepancy was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), suggesting a greater occurrence of subclinical hypothyroidism in individuals with metabolic syndrome.

Thyroid Function Tests

- TSH Levels: The average TSH level was considerably greater in the group with metabolic syndrome (4.5 mIU/L) compared to the control group (2.8 mIU/L) ($p < 0.01$).
- Free T4 Levels: The mean free T4 levels did not show any significant variation between the two groups and remained within the normal range.

Metabolic Syndrome Parameters

- Blood Pressure: Individuals diagnosed with metabolic syndrome exhibited markedly elevated systolic and diastolic blood pressures in comparison to the control group.
- The metabolic syndrome group exhibited elevated triglyceride levels and decreased HDL cholesterol levels, which are consistent with the diagnostic criteria for this illness.
- Glucose Levels: The metabolic syndrome group exhibited significantly elevated fasting glucose levels.

Association Analysis: After adjusting for age, sex, and BMI, a multivariate logistic regression analysis showed that those with metabolic syndrome had a 2.9 times higher likelihood of having subclinical hypothyroidism compared to those without metabolic syndrome. The odds ratio was 2.9, with a 95% confidence interval of 1.3 to 6.5, and a p-value of less than 0.01.

Group	Sample Size	Prevalence of Subclinical Hypothyroidism	Mean TSH (mIU/L)	Mean Free T4 (ng/dL)	Odds Ratio (95% CI)	p-value
Metabolic Syndrome	100	22%	4.5	Normal range	2.9 (1.3-6.5)	< 0.01
Non-Metabolic Syndrome	100	8%	2.8	Normal range	N/A	< 0.05

The study highlighted a significantly higher prevalence of subclinical hypothyroidism among patients with metabolic syndrome compared to the control group. The odds of having subclinical hypothyroidism were approximately 2.9 times higher in the metabolic syndrome group. TSH levels were also notably higher in the metabolic syndrome group, while Free T4 levels remained within the normal range across both groups. The p-values indicate statistical significance in the findings.

Figure 1: The bar graph displays the prevalence of subclinical hypothyroidism and the mean TSH levels for patients with and without metabolic syndrome. The blue bars represent the prevalence percentages, and the red line shows the mean TSH levels for each group.

Discussion

The study's results demonstrate a substantial correlation between subclinical hypothyroidism and metabolic syndrome, indicating a greater occurrence of thyroid dysfunction in patients with metabolic syndrome as opposed to those without it [9]. The presence of increased TSH levels in individuals with metabolic syndrome indicates a potential disruption in the thyroid axis, which could either worsen or contribute to the metabolic imbalances associated with this illness [10,11]. The lack of notable disparities in free T4 levels between the two groups strengthens the notion that the thyroid dysfunction is subclinical, meaning that peripheral thyroid hormone levels stay within the normal range despite an elevated TSH [12].

The findings align with other research indicating that even little thyroid malfunction might impact metabolic processes, presumably via affecting lipid metabolism, insulin resistance, and blood pressure regulation [13]. The elevated odds ratio for subclinical hypothyroidism in the metabolic syndrome group highlights the possibility of conducting thyroid screening in this population [14]. This could result in early detection and treatment of thyroid dysfunction, reducing the likelihood of developing more severe thyroid diseases or worsening metabolic syndrome components [15].

Moreover, the notable disparities in lipid profiles, blood glucose levels, and blood pressure among the groups correspond to the distinguishing features of metabolic syndrome and underscore the complex risk profile of these patients [16]. The study's findings suggest that incorporating integrated care strategies that target both thyroid and metabolic health could lead to enhanced results for patients in clinical practice [17]. Future study should investigate longitudinal data to determine causality and evaluate the effects of thyroid hormone treatment on metabolic syndrome outcomes. This will help us gain a better understanding of the relationship between these intricate illnesses [18-20].

Conclusion

Researchers found that metabolic syndrome patients have a greater risk of subclinical hypothyroidism than those without, suggesting a link between the two illnesses. Elevated TSH levels in metabolic syndrome patients suggest thyroid dysfunction may worsen metabolic abnormalities. These findings suggest frequent thyroid function monitoring in metabolic syndrome patients to detect and treat subclinical hypothyroidism. Healthcare practitioners can enhance metabolic profile and lower metabolic syndrome-related cardiovascular risks by aggressively addressing thyroid health. Further longitudinal investigations are needed to determine causal linkages and thyroid function therapy efficacy in this patient population.

References

1. Surks MI, Ortiz E, Daniels GH, Sawin CT, Col NF, Cobin RH, et al. Subclinical thyroid disease: scientific review and guidelines for diagnosis and management. *JAMA*. 2004;291(2):228-38.
2. Rodondi N, den Elzen WP, Bauer DC, Cappola AR, Razvi S, Walsh JP, et al. Subclinical hypothyroidism and the risk of coronary heart disease and mortality. *JAMA*. 2010;304(12):1365-74.
3. Grundy SM, Cleeman JI, Daniels SR, Donato KA, Eckel RH, Franklin BA, et al. Diagnosis and management of the metabolic syndrome: an American Heart Association/National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute Scientific Statement. *Circulation*. 2005;112(17):2735-52.
4. Biondi B, Cooper DS. The clinical significance of subclinical thyroid dysfunction. *Endocr Rev*. 2008 Feb;29(1):76-131.
5. Hak AE, Pols HA, Visser TJ, Drexhage HA, Hofman A, Witteman JC. Subclinical hypothyroidism is an independent risk factor for atherosclerosis and myocardial infarction in elderly women: the Rotterdam Study. *Ann Intern Med*. 2000 Feb 15;132(4):270-8.
6. Gencer B, Collet TH, Virgini V, Bauer DC, Gussekloo J, Cappola AR, et al. Subclinical thyroid dysfunction and the risk of heart failure events: an individual participant data analysis from 6 prospective cohorts. *Circulation*. 2012 Aug 28;126(9):1040-9.
7. O'Brien T, Dinneen SF, O'Brien PC, Palumbo PJ. Hyperlipidemia in patients with primary and secondary hypothyroidism. *Mayo Clin Proc*. 1993 Sep;68(9):860-6.
8. Pearce EN. Hypothyroidism and dyslipidemia: modern concepts and approaches. *Curr Cardiol Rep*. 2004 Jul;6(6):451-6.
9. Cappola AR, Ladenson PW. Hypothyroidism and atherosclerosis. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2003 Jun;88(6):2438-44.
10. Rizos CV, Elisaf MS, Liberopoulos EN. Effects of thyroid dysfunction on lipid profile. *Open Cardiovasc Med J*. 2011; 5:76-84.
11. Canaris GJ, Manowitz NR, Mayor G, Ridgway EC. The Colorado thyroid disease prevalence study. *Arch Intern Med*. 2000 Feb 28;160(4):526-34.
12. Singh S, Duggal J, Molnar J, Maldonado F, Barsano CP, Arora R. Impact of subclinical thyroid disorders on coronary heart disease, cardiovascular and all-cause mortality: a meta-analysis. *Int J Cardiol*. 2008 Mar 14;125(1):41-8.
13. Imaizumi M, Akahoshi M, Ichimaru S, Nakashima E, Hida A, Soda M, et al. Risk for ischemic heart disease and all-cause mortality in subclinical hypothyroidism. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2004 Jul;89(7):3365-70.
14. Monzani F, Di Bello V, Caraccio N, Bertini A, Giorgi D, Giusti C, et al. Effect of levothyroxine replacement on lipid profile and intima-media thickness in subclinical hypothyroidism: a double-blind, placebo-controlled study. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2004 May;89(5):2099-106.
15. Völzke H, Robinson DM, Spielhagen T, Nauck M, Obst A, Ewert R, et al. Are serum thyrotropin levels within the reference range associated with visceral and subcutaneous adiposity in German adults? *Eur J Endocrinol*. 2009 May;160(5):731-7.
16. Walsh JP, Bremner AP, Bulsara MK, O'Leary P, Leedman PJ, Feddema P, et al. Subclinical thyroid dysfunction as a risk factor for cardiovascular disease. *Arch Intern Med*. 2005 Nov 28;165(21):2467-72.
17. Gussekloo J, van Exel E, de Craen AJ, Meinders AE, Frölich M, Westendorp RG. Thyroid status, disability and cognitive function, and survival in old age. *JAMA*. 2004 Dec 1;292(21):2591-9.
18. Boekholdt SM, Titan SM, Wiersinga WM, Chatterjee K, Basart DC, Luben R, et al. Initial thyroid status and cardiovascular risk factors: the EPIC-Norfolk prospective population study. *Clin Endocrinol (Oxf)*. 2010 Mar; 72(3):404-10.
19. Asvold BO, Vatten LJ, Nilsen TI, Bjørø T. The association between TSH within the reference range and serum lipid concentrations in a population-based study. The HUNT Study. *Eur J Endocrinol*. 2007 Feb;156(2):181-6.
20. Diez JJ, Iglesias P. Spontaneous normalization of thyrotropin concentrations in patients with subclinical hypothyroidism. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2001 Jun;86(6).